

The mechanism by which stars create hydrogen.

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Abstract

This paper sets out the mechanism by which hydrogen is created in the outer layers of stars. Hydrogen creation begins with $[e^-, e^+]$ pair production from high energy photons. The spin of an electron is flipped in the star's magnetic field before it can annihilate with a positron (to return a photon). The model for the electron used in this paper comprises half a photon trapped in a temporal discontinuity (along its axis). A chain of $[e^+, e^-, e^+]$ can form where the polarised poles of the electron come together and lock with poles of two positrons to create a heavy particle.

The relative electrical potential energy between an electron and a positron is the source of the energy in the rest mass of a proton or neutron. The energy is confined by stretching space between the poles of the electron. The half photon in one of the positrons is then given up to a passing neutrino leaving the chain $[e^+, e^-, \nu]$ which then closes to form a neutron.

In familiar terms the gluons in protons and neutrons are stretched portions of space-time (a *Heisenberg-strut* would be a preferable name) held apart by quarks (a Heaviside ball would be a preferable name). Quarks are locked pairs of poles (one originating from an electron, the other from a positron) termed *g-bits*. *The energy used to stretch the space-time links comes from the electric potential of the g-bit at the temporal ends of the electron and positron pairs. The Heisenberg-struts have properties that mirror gluons in their range of link types but do not have made up nonsense names to cloud the fact that the origin of their properties is not understood.*

The continuous creation model of the cosmos fell from favour due to the lack of a credible mechanism by which mass and energy are created. This paper solves that by setting out the basic pathway for primary hydrogen creation in stars.

Keywords: *how stars create their own hydrogen. worm holes in particles, what a quark is, reaction mass less star drive, gamma source fusion reactor, Hobson star drive.*

1 Introduction

85% of stars exist in binary pairs. This single fact alone is incompatible with the: *some native dust and hydrogen field clumping together to form stars* model after a *big bang*. Even second sequence stars that formed from supernova ejecta and untracked hydrogen fields are unlikely to form pairs of independent accretion disks with velocities that let them orbit each other. Clearly another process is at work in star and galaxy formation.

Continuous creation models in which space-time, mass and energy are locally created in some cascade process provide models that more readily accounts for the patchy, structured nature of the cosmos. What was missing from these models was (until now) any reasonable account of how mass and energy are created.

This paper sets out how hydrogen (and neutrons), the primary fuel source of stars, is created by a star itself.

The process requires most of quantum theory to be abandoned in favour of admitting the existence of explicit structure within the electron. This structure requires a local discontinuity in space-time. The *thing* that distinguishes a particle from an electromagnetic wave is the presence of one or more local discontinuities in space time in the particle.

This paper presents a candidate model for the form of a circularly polarised photon together with a description of how a particle forms when a photon 'breaks in two' in a pair creation event (section 2). Each particle holds half a photon trapped by reflection from a broken bit of space time (a *g-bit*). This particle is not created instantaneously but forms as the half photon reflects off the broken end. This accounts for the initial straight portion of a created pair's tracks in cloud chamber observations.

The hydrogen creation pathway is presented in its constituent parts, section 2 looks at pair production from high energy photon scattering events, section 2.3 provides a model of the electron that includes intrinsic angular momentum and a mechanism for *spin flip*. Section 3 looks at how the *g-bits* at the temporally separated ends of electrons and positrons may be brought together to harness the potential energy available from *near-point charges*. *Section 3 speculates on how a triple of e^+, e^-, e^+ might come to be closed to form a e^+, e^-, ν ring or a neutron. Standard neutron decay into a proton via passing off the half photon in electron completes the process.*

The most striking failure in Physics is how the missing mechanics of the pair-creation event have been hidden behind a Feynman diagram.

Conclusions are offered in section 8.

2 Pair-Production from high energy photons

Pair production from high energy photon scattering is historically treated as a black box with little detail of the actual mechanism by which a photon is transformed into a e^-, e^+ pair being offered. A historical perspective reviewing the thought on pair-production is given in [7]. e^-, e^+ pair-production requires a minimum photon energy of 1.022MeV for scattering from a nucleus or 2.0MeV for scattering from an electron or higher for photon on photon scattering. Pair production is readily witnessed in cloud chambers with gamma rays from the decay of cobalt 60. The pair production event is easily summarised in a Feynman penguin diagram [5]. This slight of hand has served to stifle genuine inquiry into: the nature of the transition process from photon to electron and also into the internal mechanism of the electron itself.

At the time of writing the author was unable to find a definitive mathematical description of the travelling EM field that constitute a single photon. The author does not recognise eigen mode descriptions of an object as a valid description of the object any more than a Fourier transform description of a soliton actually describes a finite soliton. Photons (single quanta of light) have well established properties, they have a wavelength λ (established from interference experiments), linear momentum, energy and intrinsic angular momentum or spin. They are able to cross vast distances in space without losing energy to changing direction, (we (NASA) can form optical images of stars 90,000,000 light years away).

- Energy: $E = hf = h\frac{c}{\lambda}$
 - E is the energy of the photon
 - h is Planck's constant
 - f is the frequency of the light
 - $\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$ is the reduced Planck constant
 - λ is the wavelength.

- $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency
- c is the speed of light
- *Momentum*: $\mathbf{p} = \frac{h}{\lambda} \hat{\mathbf{n}} = \frac{E}{c} \hat{\mathbf{n}}$
 - \mathbf{p} is the momentum vector
 - $\hat{\mathbf{n}}$ is a unit vector in the direction of propagation
- *Angular Momentum (Spin)*: $S = \pm\hbar$
 - The photon has a spin of ± 1 unit of angular momentum irrespective of the wavelength of the photon.

It is worth noting that diffraction patterns are a function of slit separation and light wavelength and do not change with polarisation angle. This implies the width of a photon is proportional to its wavelength and this is in agreement with the angular momentum of all photons being $\pm\hbar$. The energy in a photon gyrates about its axis of propagation (for a fuller explanation of the angular momentum in a photon see [8]).

Figure 2 shows a visualisation the electric field of single circularly polarised photon. The profile of this illustration is $E(t, y, z) = [t, \|\sin(t)\| * \cos(t), \|\sin(t)\| * \sin(t)]$ for $t = [-\pi, \pi]$.

Electrons and positrons each have an intrinsic angular momentum of $\pm\frac{\hbar}{2}$. This paper puts forward the idea that you get an electron and a positron each with half the angular momentum of a circularly polarised photon if you break the photon at the origin in the figure 2. It is not straightforward to uniquely define the companion magnetic field that accompanies the illustrative photon as it propagates through space. In reality the profile may not be a strict sign wave but rather some form of soliton and it is beyond the scope of this paper to offer a definitive description of the EM fields in a single photon.

This general form of photon has 3 distinguished points where the electric field is 0. These points accurately define a straight line. This kind of photon is very likely to have a stable direction of travel. It is likely to be non-dispersive because all of the displacement current within the photon must pass through these axial points.

Maxwell's equations are written in their differential form as,

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} &= \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \text{ (Gauss's Law)} \\ \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= 0 \text{ (Gauss's Law for Magnetism)} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \text{ (Faraday's Law)} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \text{ (Ampère-Maxwell's Law)}.\end{aligned}$$

This paper essentially argues that electric charge is the result of polarisation of a g-bit of space time rather than being some magical thing that just exists without explanation. The version of Maxwell's equations where for convenience magnetic monopoles can exist are:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0 \rho_m \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \mu_0 \mathbf{J}_m\end{aligned}$$

It would be easy to speculate that the tips of a photon are effectively rotating magnetic monopoles i.e. $\mathbf{J}_m \neq \mathbf{0}$ just in a $\mathbf{N} - \mathbf{S}$ pair with in each half of the photon. Again it is beyond the scope of this paper to prove or disprove this.

Figure 1: Illustrative single photon electric field, blue is +ve potential, red is -ve. The 5 views are from slightly different angles. Angular momentum results form off axis distribution of energy as the field rotates.

If no electric charge is present magnetic potential is related to the displacement current:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{t}) = \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{t})}{\partial t} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq \frac{\lambda}{2} \quad (1)$$

The magnetic field is perpendicular to the rate of change of electric field (referred to by Maxwell as the 'displacement current').

2.1 Half Photon Particle Formation

Assuming a photon can be 'broken' at a point what does this actually mean? Presumably the back half of the break somehow gobbles up the axial component of photon. The rotational component presumably continues rotating. This presumably means that the relative time at which the different values of the electric field existed in the photon must somehow remain present in the new particle.

The displacement current

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t})}{\partial t} \cdot \mathbf{x}$$

at the break presumably raises the electric potential of a point in space time while the perpendicular component carries on in time.

$$\mathbf{E}(x, y, z, t) = [x - t, \|\sin((x - t))\| * \cos(x - t), \|\sin(x - t)\| * \sin(x - t)] \text{ for } t = [0, \pi]. \quad (2)$$

as a description of the electric field in half a single photon the displacement current is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t})}{\partial t} = (-1, -\cos(2(x - t)), -\sin(2(x - t)))$$

reflecting this in $x - t$:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{E}'(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{t})}{\partial t} = (1, -\cos(2(x + t)), \sin(2(x + t)))$$

Giving a wave propagating backwards in time. Adding the two displacement currents together gives a wave with no velocity in \mathbf{x} .

The change in electrical potential of the back face of the break will presumably be the integral along \mathbf{x} over the half photon. The position of the back face that is reflecting the wave must change to account for the momentum of the original half photon. The process presumably completes when the reflected wave overlaps with the collapsing wave.

The object that results holds a rotating electric field that alternately propagates forwards in time and backwards in time between two poles. The poles exist at different times while being in some way coincident.

Figure 2.1 attempts to show the resulting object.

2.2 Particle Tracks.

I do not have publication right for a cloud (or bubble) chamber image of the tracks create during pair creation. From looking at published images of such tracks it appears that the paths taken by the electron and positron start straight and gradually begin to curve in the presence of the magnetic field in the cloud chamber.

This supports the idea that it takes time for the electron to collapse into its standing wave form (charge appears as the poles of the electron/positron are polarised).

The track seem broadly consistent with what happens when a rotating bar breaks in two (angular momentum is conserved as two independent chunks go their separate ways).

The angle between the two paths will be a function of the details of the scattering event.

2.3 The Poles of the Electron.

Electrons have poles. Their measured properties include angular momentum (labelled as spin) and a magnetic dipole moment. Their magnetic dipole moment can be aligned $N\text{-}z\text{-}S$ along the axis of rotation spin $+1/2$ (with right handed rotation) or $S\text{-}z\text{-}N$ spin $-1/2$ (again aligned with right handed rotation). The angular momentum present in an electron is accounted for by the angular momentum present in half a photon. Electrons can be observed flipping their magnetic dipole moment relative to their angular momentum in the presence of a magnetic field and emitting a photon of a characteristic wavelength [10, 6]. Photon associated with this spin flip have a

Figure 2: Illustrative rotating electric field propagating forwards and backwards in time. The red arrows represent the value of the electric field as it propagate forwards in time, the blue arrows represent the field propagating backwards in time. The electron is the captured standing wave of half a photon.

wavelength of 21cm and this can readily be detected as part of the cosmic microwave background spectra.

Spin flip is not a property that would be predicted if the magnetic dipole moment of the electron arose from the rotating EM field inside an electron. Cooper pairs involve electrons adopting opposite spins [3] when they pair up.

This paper proposes that the poles of an electron are quanta of space time. They are the smallest piece of space time capable of supporting a raised electric potential and a magnetic dipole moment. It is further proposed that there is a maximum electric potential a quantised chunk of space time is capable of supporting (and the same is probably true for magnetic flux).

The this is new physics so the model proposed here may not fully represent reality but actively representing electron poles should lead to a better model than a model of an electron totally lacking on poles.

The new physics in the paper is the idea that the poles of the electron exist at different times, one exists in the future and the other in the past. The self energy in the electron is stretched time, held apart by the self repulsion of the charges poles. Figure 2.3 shows a putative g-bit of space time. Free space can clearly support the presence of a magnetic field but it is less clear how a magnetic field can pass from one point to the next if the field is spreading out and becoming weaker. At a point the range of angles of the incoming magnetic field must be less than the outgoing field, this means that there has to be some means of different sides of a g-bit having independent magnetic flux connections. This seems to imply that the surface of a g-bit behaves like a collection of linked magnetic monopoles (or a bundle of dipoles).

For the purposes of this paper the exact nature of magnetic flux propagation is just glossed over but what is clear is $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ for a g-bit holds in aggregate and a g-bit can support a magnetic dipole moment. The chiral nature of the proposed g-bit seems to imply that electric potential is not uniformly distributed with in a g-bit in which case it is possible for spin up and spin down electrons to have two distinct energy states.

g-bit of space time.

Figure 3: A *g-bit* of space-time. It supports the transit electromagnetic fields, displacement currents that create magnetic fields. (It supports chirality wrt displacement currents.)

2.4 Rest Mass of the Electron and spin flip.

Rest mass of the electron results from the stretching of time between the poles of the electron. The repulsive force between the two poles of the electron arises from the electric polarisation of the faces of the two poles of the electron. Charge per say does not exist as an abstract thing only polarisation of a quanta of space time.

The quantisation of charge is an artefact of the quantisation of space-time and a limit on how much polarisation a quanta of space-time can support. Figure 2.4

Figure 2.4 attempts to show the time looped particle.

Again we resort to penguin arm flapping here and assume we can make an equivalence between separation in distance and in time for electrostatic forces as $dt = dr/c$. Python code for the self energy of the stretched space time between the two poles of the the electron gives a time separation of the poles and a putative figure for the rest mass of a neutrino.

```
import numpy as np
import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
# Constants
q = 1.602176634e-19          # Charge of an electron (C)
epsilon_0 = 8.8541878128e-12 # Vacuum permittivity (F/m)
m = 9.1093837015e-31        # Mass of an electron (kg)
c = 299792458               # Speed of light (m/s)
k = 8.98755179e9            # Coulomb's constant
mvj = 1.602176634e-13
h = 6.62607015e-34;        # Planck's constant
Uj = m * c**2               # rest mass energy of electron

print('rest mass in Joules')
print( Uj)

print('self energy of two point charges e/2 = Uj  separated by r')
B2r = k*(q/2) *(q/2)/Uj
```

The electron as a time dualled g-bit.

Figure 4: A time dualled *g-bit* of space-time. The upper and lower *g-bits* are the same particle but with displacement current flowing the opposite direction in time. The mutually repulsive force of the two point potentials is balanced by the Heisenberg struts. The Heisenberg struts carry the displacement current forward and backwards in time.

```

print(B2r)

EspinFlip = 9.41170815267813e-25 #joules

# difference in efective radius
B2rf = k * q * q/((Uj - EspinFlip)*4)

print('spatial quantization size')
dr = B2rf - B2r
print(dr)

# separation of distance r in time dimension.
print('separation of distance r in time dimension. dt')
dt_r = B2r/c
print(dt_r)

# Heisenberg strut spring constant.
# force of replusion between 2 point charges a distance r apart.

# F = k * (q1 * q2) / r^2
# assuming a linear spring constant for time displacement.
# F = Hs * dt.

```

```

F = k * (q * q) / (4 * B2r**2)
print('force in N')
print(F)
Hs = F / (B2r)
print('Heisenberg spring constant in N/m')
print(Hs)

# rest mass of neutrino
Un = (Hs*dr**2)/2
Mn = Un/(c**2)

print('rest mass of neutrino')
print(Mn)

--- output ---
rest mass in Joules
8.187105776823886e-14
self energy of two point charges e/2 = Uj separated by r
7.044850813739913e-16
spatial quantization size
8.09854466061206e-27
separation of distance r in time dimension. dt
2.3499092874911193e-24
force in N
116.21404048551571
Heisenberg spring constant in N/m
1.6496309653407827e+17
rest mass of neutrino
6.019069551327487e-53

```

Figure 2.4 illustrates how the Heisenberg struts are stretched depending on which side of the g-bit the electric potential appears. The spring constant of the Heisenberg struts will balance self repulsion of the potentials. To a first approximation the difference in self energy can be taken as a change in separation.

Spin flip of an electron (or positron) involves rotating each pole of the electron through 180 degrees to reverse the direction of the magnetic dipole of the particle without changing the angular momentum.

2.5 Where is the near-point charged surface hiding?

The model of the electron proposed in this paper has physical poles. Ordinarily you would expect these poles to be observable in scattering events if they existed. The answer is of course that the poles do not exist in the present, they exist in the future and in the past and information cycles forwards and backwards in time between them. Particles retain a record of their own motion. The inherent temporal discontinuity in particles makes writing a Lagrangian for them a future task. Accelerating a particle involves stretching space time between the temporal ends of the particle.

This paper assumes distance in time can be treated as just another orthogonal dimension (scaled by c, the speed of light) for the purposes of calculating electric potential. If an electric charge is off the time plane by time dt then the electric potential V at a point a distance r from the point in space becomes.

Figure 5: The difference between spin up spin down electrons. The Heisenberg struts are stretched while the apparent charge separation remains constant. To a first approximation the difference in self energy is a function of the change in Heisenberg strut length.

$$V = \frac{kq}{\sqrt{r^2 + (dt * c)^2}} \quad (3)$$

For a stationary electron the electric potential at a distance from a dualled g-bit at a distance dt from the current time plane would be

$$V = \frac{2kq}{\sqrt{r^2 + (dt * c)^2}} \quad (4)$$

Where q is half of the charge on electron. This is a much friendlier potential than a naked $1/r$ or $1/r^2$ one. Python to plot this kind of function is:

```
import numpy as np
```

```

import math
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Define the function
def f(r):
    return 1 / np.sqrt(r**2 + 1)

def g(r):
    gs = np.absolute( 1/r)
    return np.minimum(3,gs)

# Generate values for r
r_values = np.linspace(-10, 10, 500) # Generate 500 points between -10 and 10

# Calculate corresponding y-values
y_values = f(r_values)
y2 = g(r_values)

# Create the plot
plt.figure()
plt.plot(r_values, y_values)
plt.plot(r_values, y2, label='min(3, 1/r)')
plt.xlabel("r")
plt.ylabel("f(r) and max(2, 1/r)")
plt.title("Plot of f(r) = 1 / sqrt(r^2 + 1)")
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.savefig('potential.eps', format='eps')

plt.show()

```

It is important to note that the 'charge' on the surface of a g-bit is counted twice.

Figure 2.5 shows a plot of a general $\frac{1}{\sqrt{r^2+1}}$ potential and a less well behaved $\frac{1}{r}$ potential. The time displacement of the charge centres neatly deals with the traditional mathematical issue of point charges.

3 Linking g-bits to form protons and neutrons

If an electron and a positron each contained a point charge then in theory there would be infinite energy available through bringing these points arbitrarily close together. This paper argues that once the spin of either particle is flipped they cannot directly recombine to form a pair of photons rather the charges faces of the g-bits may approach but not touch each other.

Neutrons readily decay into a proton, an electron and an anti-neutrino when in free space. The half life of this decay is quoted to be 14min 11sec [11]. In reality what happens is some part of the electron half-photon present in the neutron jumps to a passing electron neutrino. The atomic weight of the neutron is 939.565 MeV and the rest mass of a proton is 938.272 MeV [9] the difference is 1.293 MeV. Both protons and neutrons have spin $\frac{1}{2}$

Figure 6: Illustrative plot of the shape of the experienced electric potential of the time dualled g-bit electron. Of course the potentials that create the field exists in the past and the future not in the now. There are no infinities in the measured field in the now.

Figure 3 illustrates the process by which protons and neutrons can form from collections of electrons and positrons. The g-bit at the pole of the electron can have state:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{time } +, \text{time } - \quad (t^+, t^-) \\
 & \text{North or South polarity} \quad (N, S) \\
 & \text{AM } + \text{ or AM } - \text{ angular momentum} \quad (A_+, A_-) \\
 & \text{Polarisation } + /- \text{ face OUT or IN} \quad (+O, +I) \text{ or } (-O, -I)
 \end{aligned}$$

So an electron can be described by the state of two g-bits, t^+ and t^- as $[t^+NA_+ - O|t^-SA_+ - O]$. Presumably if an electron is to mate non destructively with a pair of positrons then the charged faces of all of the g-bits must be inwards and the mating poles should be should be N-S paired. In truth the mating process is guess work but there is ample electric potential available to stretch space into gluons (or Heisenberg struts) to create rest mass given the estimated size of a g-bit of $8.1 \times 10^{-27} \text{m}$ (there is no suggestion of a point potential in a g-bit). You need a chain of $[e^+, e^-, e^+]$ to provide a pulling force to stretch the spatial dimension of the Heisenberg Struts in the inner electron. Whether mating faces are paired t^+, t^- or t^+, t^+ is also to be determined.

This paper proposes that the gluon (Heisenberg struts) stretching and quark (Heaviside ball) formation process 3 is: a triple of $[e^+, e^-, e^+]$ line up, their spins are such that neither of the e^+, e^- pairings can annihilate into photons, the N g-bit pole of the electron (with its charged face facing inwards) locks with the S g-bit pole of a positron (again with charged face facing inwards) and likewise for the S pole of the electron g-bit. The spin of the particles then all flip locking them together. The half photon inside on of the positrons then hops onto a passing neutrino (or leaves in some other way) and the poles of that positron then sympathetically polarise with those of the electron and the remaining polarised ends of the particle close to form a ring (a neutron). The free neutron can then either decay into a proton (by shedding a half photon or pair up with a proton in a hydrogen nucleus. The onward fusion of hydrogen into other stuff is standard physics. The huge neutrino flux from the sun would seem to suggest that electrons and positrons are relatively profligate in shedding their half photons.

Figure 7: A guess at the mechanics of nucleon formation from electrons and positrons. The temporal discontinuity between the poles of the electron have to be stretched and the g-bit form one end of the electron must 'lock' with the g-bit of a positron.

3.1 Estimating the size of a quark

A crude estimate of quark size can be had by calculating how close together you need to bring the charge on the two g-bits end to release energy equivalent to half the rest mass of the neutron.

$$r = k * (q/2) * (q/2) / (m_{\text{neutron}}/2)$$

or about $r = 0.766 * 10^{-18}m$. This is in ballpark agreement with the experimentally determined size of a quark of $< 0.4310^{-18}$ meters as r represents a predicted maximum size (energy could be lost/released during the mating process requiring a closer approach).

4 The energy budget of a star

The hydrogen creation pathway outlined in the paper creates a potentially limitless amount of energy. It is assumed that the high energy photons required to produce the initial blanket of hydrogen round a star come from heavy element decay in the star's inner layers. In broad terms:

1. 1.1MeV photon \rightarrow e^+ and e^-
2. e^+ and 2 e^- + neutrino \rightarrow neutron and e^- (940 MeV of mass)
3. neutron + neutrino \rightarrow proton and e^- (938.3 + 0.5 MeV of mass + 0.8MeV of energy)
4. 2 of (proton + neutron + electron) \rightarrow 3728.4MeV of mass and 28.30MeV of energy.
5. Energy profit $4 * 1.1\text{MeV} \rightarrow$ 3756.4MeV

The star turns 4.4MeV of photon into 3728.4MeV of mass and 28.30MeV of energy with at least some of the spare energy being available as heat. Presumably small sub star gas giants like Jupiter have cores that produce enough high energy photons to create a hydrogen/helium mantle and are heavy enough to retain it but lack the gravity to burn the helium they produce.

5 Random observations not consistent with the big bang

How many times doe a model have to fail in its predictions before you admit the model is wrong? The answer would be three.

Here are three observations of the cosmos that are not compatible with the single event production of matter (the insulting Big Bang theory).

- 1. Beyond the general lumpy structure of the universe and the observation that 85% of the stars in the universe exist in binary pairs is at odds with any accretion disk model for star formation from primary material.*
- 2. Jupiter radiates twice as much heat as it receives from the sun and its atmosphere is a mixture of hydrogen (90% and helium 10% [2].*
- 3. A solitary black hole has been observed and it appears black holes create the mass they swallow [12].*
- 4. The existence of effects attributed to 'dark energy' [4].*
- 5. Photons have been measured to experience negative time by propagating through heavy nuclei [1].*

If the Big Bang theory is nonsense then so are the nostrums of quantum theory, there are no anti-particles and wave functions, however precious, do not accurately represent what is happening at a sub-atomic level.

6 The Obvious Reaction Mass less Star Drive

The hydrogen fuel cycle outlined in this paper is the only viable 'star drive'. The mark up in stored energy to reaction mass and energy of a factor of 1000 is too large to be ignored. The magnetic corona on the surface of the sun are presumable associated with 'blooms' of e^- , e^+ pair creation (which creates large currents that translate into large magnetic fields). The core initial size of these blooms presumably gives an estimate of the upper size limit of a stable star drive (a couple of kilometres). The author would like this form of star drive to be referred to as a Hobson gamma-hydrogen cycle reaction mass less star drive.

Hydrogen creation on Jupiter probably provides a better model for a practical pair-creation hydrogen cycle star drive (as the atmospheric pressure is lower than in the mantle of our sun) or even a more practical terrestrial fusion reactor. It may be a lot more practical to produce hydrogen/helium from gamma rays than to fuse deuterium.

7 Future Work

The fine detail of the model for the electron has to be cleared up. Without this there can be no real Physics.

8 Conclusions

This paper proposes a mechanism by which electrons and positrons may be fused to create protons and neutrons. This is a plausible description of the mechanism by which stars create hydrogen and helium from high energy gamma rays form their core.

This paper provides half a model for a single photon (it is missing a model for the associated magnetic fields) that has $1/2$ unit angular momentum and strong directional stability. The half photon trapped in a temporal discontinuity model accounts for the angular momentum and the magnetic moment of an electron. This paper offers an explanation of what a neutrino is as well as what quarks (Heaviside balls) and gluons (Heisenberg struts) are.

The new reaction pathway offers a possible route to a reaction mass less star drive or a new kind of fusion reactor and the discontinuity in space time model for particles could be expanded to describe more exotic short lived particles found trying to escape from particle accelerators.

Perhaps the worst delusion of the bad science that Physics has become is the worship of gauge theories in filtering mathematical descriptions of particles. Given that particles contain discontinuities in space time ANYTHING that obeys a gauge theory is guaranteed not to describe a particle.

The detail in this paper is by no means complete but it at least provides a set of pointers back towards reality.

9 Acknowledgements

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